

HORIZON 2020

Coordination and Support Action

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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

Deliverable 4.2

**Integrated pan-European communication and
engagement delivery plan**

Submission of Deliverable

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Executive Summary

From 2015-2020, *EU-PolarNet* will develop and deliver a strategic framework and mechanisms to prioritise science, optimise the use of polar infrastructure, and broker new partnerships that will lead to the co-design of polar research projects that deliver tangible benefits for society.

This integrated pan-European communication and delivery plan taps into existing communication and engagement programmes of the partner institutions; takes advantage of their stakeholder networks; benefits from their experience and expertise in the fields of science communication, stakeholder engagement, as well as media and public engagement. Coordinating these institutional assets takes forward the aspirations of EU-PolarNet.

Three strands of work form the basis of this plan:

- Corporate – generating global visibility for *EU-PolarNet*
- Internal – facilitating effective communication between participant institutions and the polar research and operations communities
- External – enabling and supporting stakeholder, media and public engagement activities

This Plan is operational from 2015 until 2020.

Introduction

Effective communications is critical for the success of *EU-PolarNet*. Work Package 4 leads on the delivery of communications and stakeholder engagement. The primary goals for *EU-PolarNet* Communications and Engagement fall into three broad areas:

- **Corporate** – generating global visibility for *EU-PolarNet*
- **Internal** – facilitating effective communication between participant institutions and the polar research and operations communities
- **External** – enabling and supporting stakeholder, media and public engagement activities

1. Purpose of this communication and engagement delivery plan is to:

- provide a strategic framework and resources to enable and support all *EU-PolarNet* participants to promote, explain, and engage stakeholders in the programme's relevance and benefits to society

2. Desired outcomes from this Plan are that:

- polar research community-engagement leads to awareness of *EU-PolarNet* ambitions for enhanced European Arctic and Antarctic research and operational coordination
- recognition that *EU-PolarNet* is a provider of strategic science policy advice to the European Commission and other international bodies
- global recognition that *EU-PolarNet* is a successful forum for shaping future polar science and operational collaborations
- *EU-PolarNet* participants' incorporate 'messaging' about the value and relevance of *EU-PolarNet* in their own national engagement and dialogue with communities, politicians, policy advisors and business sectors
- *EU-PolarNet* participants understand how best to engage with target stakeholder sectors
- target stakeholder sectors understand how they can connect with *EU-PolarNet* and EPB
- evidence of positive engagement and media coverage about *EU-PolarNet*

An action plan is outlined in Table 1.

3. Target stakeholders/audiences

The range of stakeholders that *EU-PolarNet* aims to engage is wide. Stakeholder engagement tasks are the responsibility of WP4. Communications action-planning sets out appropriate channels for particular groups or sectors; lists key messages that are

relevant to each group; and suggests different options for engaging each sector. See Table 2.

Key Stakeholders include:

- Research communities - from institutions, universities and national polar operators
- Parliamentary and policy - European Commission, the European Parliament; national governments within member states
- Business and Industry sectors - such as shipping, oil, gas, fisheries and tourism;
- European public - including young people;
- Local Arctic communities; indigenous communities
- Polar organisations including IASC, SCAR, IASSA, Arctic Council, Antarctic Treaty Secretariat etc.;
- NGOs
- International networks and agencies such as the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP); the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO), INTERACT
- The media

4. Key messages about EU-PolarNet

- *EU-PolarNet* provides opportunities to shape future EU-funded polar research initiatives
- EU-PolarNet will develop and sustain an ongoing dialogue and co-operation with all Polar stakeholders
- Outcomes from this Coordinating Action fits with European policy narratives for climate security/energy security/food and water security, human health and environment, sustainable development and economic growth
- Arctic and Antarctic research is important and relevant to European business and has potential to benefit the European economy
- European nations working together to shape future science deliver more effective operations
- Arctic and Antarctic research is exciting, important and relevant to everyone
- *EU-PolarNet* members invest in the next generation

5. Implementation and action planning

Tables 1 & 2 outline key actions and suggested activities.

6. Evaluation

Statistical analytics and stakeholder feedback mechanisms will be used to assess performance of this plan against its objectives.

7. Risks

There is a risk of fragmented activity or patchy activity across the Work Packages or participating organisations. This will be mitigated by good co-ordination; agreed key messages and activities that will be reported regularly to WP1 (AWI).

Table 1. Action Plan

Objective	Action	Lead institution	Status
Generating European and international visibility	create editorial narrative & key messages and visual assets (banners, leaflets, logo-branded presentations etc)	BAS	Completed
	encourage all participants to use editorial narrative and key messages in their own communications activity	All	
	create an online presence – www.eu-polarnet.eu	BAS-AWI	Completed
	encourage all programme participants to create appropriate content about their involvement in EU-PolarNet and include reciprocal links on their own websites to drive e-traffic back to www.eu-polarnet.eu	All	
	create a social media presence including on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn	AWI-BAS	Completed
	create a ‘science and society’ and education links page on www.eu-polarnet.eu to aggregate relevant content on participants’ national websites and allow visitors to see existing effort and resources	AWI-BAS	
	Consider translating some EU-PolarNet content on non-English-language participant’s websites	All	
Guidance, support and toolkit for participants	Create a member only area on the EU-PolarNet website and on Dropbox	AWI	Complete

	Establish a network of communications professionals from all participating organisations	BAS-AWI	Completed
	Ensure that participants use their own communications networks and channels to boost awareness of <i>EU-PolarNet</i> and its ambitions		In progress
	Create a ‘Communications toolkit’ with photographic and video images that can be shared free-of-charge; key messages; guidance notes; logos etc.	BAS-AWI	In progress
	Write a series of key messages, tailored to stakeholder sectors about the programme	BAS	Completed
Stakeholder engagement actions	create a newsletter for participants and selected stakeholders	BAS-AWI	In progress
	ensure that appropriate ‘signposts’ hyperlinks to related material on participants’ websites are clear on the www.eu-polarnet.eu	(WP4)	
	create a Stakeholder map and develop key messages and web editorial content targeted at these groups	(WP4)	
	identify appropriate mechanisms and channels for facilitating knowledge exchange between the <i>EU-PolarNet’s</i> scientific community and stakeholder sectors	(WP4)	
	Develop a ‘communications timeline’ to identify engagement opportunities, key milestones and events. (Outreach activities should be performed to reach the different types of stakeholders and to promote an ongoing dialogue.)		

Media communication	<p>Use the network of participants' communications offices to generate news stories for media and online audiences; as well as public engagement events/activities</p> <p>The press offices or communication responsible persons in each institution or country will work collectively to coordinate press releases, press conferences, interviews with researchers, media relationships, where appropriate.</p>	Communications officers' network to coordinate	
Public engagement and face-to-face activities	<p>Public engagement activities should be performed in each participant's country. As far as possible, each institution should organize one outreach activity per year to promote its involvement in <i>EU-PolarNet</i>.</p>		

Table 2. Example activities

Note: this list is indicative of the type of activity and outcome. It is not exhaustive.

Type of activity and Key message	Target Stakeholder(s)	Desired Outcome	Delivery mechanism/channel	Led by	Evaluation metric
<p>Peer-to-peer communication/engagement Academic workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks • Collaboration and partnership • Peer-reviewed publishing <p>Key message: <i>EU-PolarNet</i> provides opportunities to shape future EU-funded polar research</p>	The European polar scientific community	Exchange of ideas, data, knowledge and best practice that advances the aims of <i>EU-PolarNet</i>	Presentation of papers and keynote addresses at relevant science conferences/events e-networks and use of collaborative tools to facilitate partnership working	Work package and task leaders	Record number of keynote presentations given/invitations to present Record the number of collaborations arising from workshops, networks and published articles
<p>Science into Policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Briefings • Dialogue • Provision of expert advice <p>Key message: <i>EU-PolarNet</i> provides opportunities to shape future polar research programmes and enhance effective operational</p>	European Parliament; national Government departments Policy/decision makers Arctic and Antarctic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politicians and policy makers acknowledge the relevance of the <i>EU-PolarNet</i> in their own communication and decision making activities 	<p>Science writing - Creation of plain-language, engaging summaries of science plans and research outcomes including</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministerial science briefings • Policy briefings 	Work Package leaders to work with <i>AWI</i> to identify opportunities for engagement with this target group.	Monitor EC/EU publications, websites and media and other sources for ministerial/govt policy references to the <i>EU-PolarNet</i>

<p>planning and use of infrastructure; it makes an important contribution to the European economy</p> <p>This research initiative fits with European policy narratives for climate security/energy security/food security etc</p>	<p>Governance bodies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct scientific input to Government policy for the Arctic • Visibility for the <i>EU-PolarNet</i> and its participants at EU and national parliamentary events/briefings (including Select Committee sessions) 	<p>NB. These must be written in a style that is relevant to the target audience.</p> <p>Parliamentary events/briefings/placements</p> <p>Partnership working with European Polar Board and national parliamentary contacts</p> <p>Online - Policy-relevant content for the <i>EU-PolarNet</i> website</p>	<p>Monitor reaction and feedback from parliamentary events</p> <p>Monitor unique visits to ‘policy-relevant’ areas of the website</p>
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Table2 continued

Note: this list is indicative of the type of activity and outcome. It is not exhaustive.

Type of activity and Key message	Target Stakeholder(s)	Desired Outcome	Delivery mechanism/channel	Led by	Evaluation metric
<p>Wealth creation for Europe</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dialogue events/activity targeted to business leaders with known Arctic/Antarctic interests • Science writing - Business briefings explaining the relevance of science to specific business areas/needs • Business workshops <p>Key message: Arctic and Antarctic research is</p>	Business & Industry	Two-way dialogue with business leaders initiated which leads to: greater understanding by scientists of the business need; to business decisions/activity informed by publication; and communication of peer-reviewed/commissioned research	<p>Face-to-Face contact and dialogue events and workshops</p> <p>E-contact through direct mailings to specific target groups</p> <p>Web delivery of relevant content</p>	<p>Work Package Leaders to work with <i>EU-PolarNet</i> coordinator to identify opportunities for engagement with this target group.</p> <p><i>WP4 & WP2</i> to identify target business groups and develop contact/dialogue activities</p>	<p>Monitor feedback from face-to-face contacts and dialogue events</p> <p>WP Leaders to report outcomes to WP1</p>

<p>important and relevant to European business and has potential to benefit the European economy</p>					
<p>Media Relations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press Releases • Feature articles • Arctic media visits • Reactive media <p>Key message: European nations working together to shape future science deliver more effective operations Arctic and Antarctic research is exciting, important and relevant to everyone</p>	<p>All target sectors</p>	<p>Global media coverage Arctic research plans and outcomes.</p> <p>Public, political & business stakeholders have opportunities to read, hear or see engaging ‘stories’ that communicate the relevance and importance of Arctic research</p>	<p>News distribution – press releases and feature stories</p> <p>Facilitate journalists visits to participants’ laboratories and offices</p> <p>Online newsroom on <i>EU-PolarNet</i> website</p>	<p><i>WP4</i> to coordinate with and participating Press Offices to develop media campaign</p> <p>WP leaders to provide plain-language summaries WP4 task leaders to coordinate media activity</p>	<p>Evaluation of media coverage</p>

Table2 continued

Note: this list is indicative of the type of activity and outcome. It is not exhaustive.

Type of activity and Key message	Target Stakeholder(s)	Desired Outcome	Delivery mechanism/channel	Led by	Evaluation metric
<p>Public Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence at Science Festivals; events including science week • Creating access to public information literature/online content • Community talks <p>Key message: polar research is exciting, important and relevant to everyone</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Members of the public • Media • Young people 	<p>Improved awareness and appreciation of the importance and relevance of polar research</p> <p>Improved understanding by the science community of public attitudes to, and confidence in, polar science</p>	<p>Exhibitions/presentations by groups of scientists at national and local events during science weeks; science festivals</p> <p>Science writing for public audiences to provide content (in print and online) that explains and promotes the importance and relevance of European polar research</p> <p>Talks and presentation to local community groups</p>	WP leaders/participants working with their organisations' communication/PR/public engagement teams	<p>Details of participation in public engagement events to be sent to the <i>EU-PolarNet</i> coordinator</p> <p>(Pro-forma return will be issued to WP leaders)</p>
<p>Enthusing young people in environmental science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of curriculum-relevant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School children • Undergrad students • PhD Students • Teachers • Parents 	Improved scientific literacy within Europe; a flow-through of next generation of environmental scientists;	www.eu-polarnet.eu to link to participants' web-based learning resources	Work package/task leaders working with their organisations' communication/public engagement/educational teams	Details of participation in EU-PolarNet specific educational activities to be sent to the <i>EU-PolarNet</i> coordinator (AWI)

<p>educational material</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in Researchers in Residence Schemes • Participation in STEM Ambassadors Scheme (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths) <p>Key message: the <i>EU-PolarNet</i> members invest in the next generation</p>		<p>Improve understanding by scientists of the requirements of students and teachers</p> <p>Rewarding experiences for scientists and young people</p>			
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